

Effect of blend of the hydrosol and latex on the property of waterborne aminoacrylic coatings

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The effect of blend of the hydrosol and latex on the property of waterborne aminoacrylic coatings was investigated. To obtain high performance waterborne aminoacrylic coatings, it is essential that the hydrosols must be compatible with the latex and have appropriate amount of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups. In order to meet these requirements, the weight-average molecular weight of the hydrosol resins should be less than 13000, and the suitable contents of AA and HEA should be about 6% and 10% by weight respectively based on all monomers. The film gloss and hardness can be improved by increasing the proportion of the hydrosols, but some disadvantages such as popping, slow-drying and abnormal high viscosity become conspicuous as weight percent of the hydrosol based on all binders exceeds 35%. The weight percent should preferably be in the range of 25 to 35% for balanced film properties.

There is a trend in the area of general coatings industry to shift from solvent-based formulations to more environmentally friendly options. Waterborne coatings represent a major direction, where the challenge is to obtain comparable or improved performance over the solvent-borne, with little or no solvent emission, and at reasonable cost. Importance has been attached to developing waterborne aminoacrylic coatings prepared from the combination of waterborne acrylic resins and melamine resins for industrial applications, especially automotives. The original water-soluble and hydrosol aminoacrylic coatings have not only desirable mechanical properties, but excellent homogeneity to provide very good appearance. These formulations, unfortunately, have some disadvantages such as slow-drying, popping upon baking and substantial levels of organic solvents which lead to VOC emissions¹. As a consequence, greater attention is being paid to aminoacrylic latex coatings consisting of hydroxyl acrylic latex, melamine resin and coalescing solvents^{2,3}. Although aminoacrylic latex coatings have advantages such as quick-drying and lower VOC emissions, it is difficult to obtain pore-free and glossy smooth film. Several patents claim that the property of aminoacrylic latex coatings can be improved by incorporating water-soluble or hydrosol or hydrosol resins⁴. This is an active field of research, but there have not been many publica-

tions in scientific literature which discuss the blending principles and factors affecting the result. This work was undertaken as an attempt to reveal the effect of molecular weight and compositions of hydrosol acrylic resins and how the weight ratio of these resins to latexes influence the properties of water-borne aminoacrylic coatings.

Results and discussion

Effect of the content of AA : The content of AA in hydrosol resins affects markedly gloss and water resistance. As can be seen in Table 1, when the content of AA exceeds 7 wt. % based on all monomers, the film gloss

Table 1. Effect of the content of AA in hydrosol resins on film properties (hydrosol : latex = 15 : 85 g/g)

AA (wt.%)	Gloss at 45°	Water resistance (h)	Impact resistance (N.cm)	Pencil hardness (H)	Adhesion (grade)
4.0	62-64	>10	>490	>2	1
5.0	61-63	>10	>490	>2	1
6.0	63-65	>10	>490	>2	1
7.0	62-64	>10	>490	>2	1
8.0	60-62	~9	>490	>2	1
10.0	58-60	~7	>490	>2	1
12.0	55-57	~7	>490	>2	1
14.0	45-47	~7	>490	>2	1

and water-resistance are poor with increasing AA contents. The preferred content of AA is 6% in this instance. The water-solubility of hydrosols improves with increasing the content of AA, which means that it becomes increasingly hydrophilic. However, too hydrophilic resins may bring about poor compatibility with the hydrophobic latex and organic pigments. This is responsible for frequent grits in coatings formed by microfloculation as well as lower film gloss. Another problem is that excessively hydrophilic resins result in a film with poor water-resistance.

Effect of molecular weight of hydrosol resins : It is found that hydrosol resins of higher molecular weight tend to lower the film gloss as shown in Table 2. Higher molecular weight resins give more viscous hydrosols which make their dispersibility in water and compatibility with the latex and pigments poor. This also brings about the microfloculation of the latex and pigments, sometimes leading to formation of grits which is responsible for poor film gloss and smoothness.

Table 2. Effect of molecular weight of hydrosol resins on film properties (hydrosol : latex = 15 : 85 g/g)

Mn/Mw	Gloss at 45°	Water resistance (h)	Impact resistance (N.cm)	Pencil hardness (H)	Adhesion (grade)
2400/6900	63–65	>10	>490	>2	1
4800/12900	62–64	>10	>490	>2	1
5800/13500	60–62	>10	>490	>2	1
7300/19200	52–54	>10	>490	>2	1

Effect of the amount of HEA : Table 3 indicates that the contents of HEA in the hydrosol resins affect obviously film water-resistance. The resins with less HEA result in poor water-resistance. HEA provides resin with crosslinkable hydroxyl groups. Crosslinking reaction between the resins and crosslinker HMMM is difficult or impossible for the hydrosol resins with little or no hydroxyl groups, thus leading to poor water-resistance.

Table 3. Effect of the amount of HEA in hydrosol resins on film properties (hydrosol : latex = 15 : 85 g/g)

HEA (wt.%)	Gloss at 45°	Water resistance (h)	Impact resistance (N.cm)	Pencil hardness (H)	Adhesion (grade)
0	63–65	~7	>490	>2	1
5	62–64	~8	>490	>2	1
10	63–65	>10	>490	>2	1

Effect of the ratio of the hydrosol to the latex : Table 4 shows that the water-resistance and gloss of the latex

Table 4. Effect of mixing weight ratio on film properties

Hydrosol (wt.%)	Gloss at 45°	Water resistance (h)	Impact resistance (N.cm)	Pencil hardness (H)	Adhesion (grade)
0	58–60	~6	>490	29.3	>1
15	63–65	>10	>490		>1
25	66–68	>10	>490	30.1	>1
35	69–71	>10	>490		>1
50	74–76	>10	>490	34.0	>1
75	79–81	>10	>490	36.9	>1
100	84–86	>10	>490	42.0	>1

film improves by increasing the proportion of the hydrosol (recipe No. 3 given in Table 7, Mn/Mw is 2400/6900). Unfortunately, it was found that some disadvantages in application properties are brought about when the weight percent of the hydrosols is more than 35%. Firstly, it is difficult to form completely dry film at RT as the film surface is still sticky after a few days. Secondly, popping on baking is conspicuous. Additionally, the brushability is poor due to abnormal high viscosity when solid contents are more than 30 wt. %, as shown in Fig. 1. The amounts of the hydrosols should preferably be in range of 25 to 35 wt. % based on all binders for better balance of properties.

Fig. 1. Viscosity variations of coatings from different blends during water dilution. Amount of the hydrosol (wt. %) : (■) 0; (□) 25; (▲) 50; (◆) 75; (●) 100.

Literature claimed that the water-soluble resins with lower molecular weight and appropriate amounts of hydrophilic groups play an important role in the stabilization of the dispersed pigments and latex particles and fill vacant spaces among latex particles⁵. The AFM images show clearly that unpigmented films of the latex and its blends with the hydrosols are smooth, but there are some imperfections on the surface of the hydrosol film, which may have been caused by popping on baking. The smooth-

ness of pigmented films of the latex is very poor, but this can be improved by incorporating the hydrosol. This fact indicates that the hydrosol has a dispersion capability for pigments.

Although the Fox Tg of the hydrosol resin (recipe No. 3 given in Table 7) is almost identical to that of the latex, the results of DSC show that the Tg of a film from the former is higher than that of the latter. This is attributed to factors as follows : firstly, the former with higher amounts of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups as active crosslinkable groups tends to form the film with higher crosslinking density than the latter with lower amounts of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups, secondly, higher amount of carboxyl group has a marked catalysis for the crosslinking reaction between film formers and HMMM, besides, better compatibility of hydrosols and HMMM is also beneficial to the crosslinking reaction, but the reaction between latexes and HMMM take place mainly at the surface of latex particles³.

Conclusions : High performance waterborne aminoacrylic coatings can be prepared using blends of well-designed hydroxyl acrylic hydrosols and hydroxyl acrylic latex as film formers and hexamethoxymethylmelamine as a crosslinker. It is very important that the hydrosols are compatible with the latex, which depends on the molecular weight and composition of the former, and have appropriate amount of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups. In our present instance, the weight-average molecular weight of the hydrosol resins should preferably be less than 13000, and the suitable contents of AA and HEA in the resins should be about 6 wt. % and 10 wt. % respectively based on all monomers. The film gloss can be improved by increasing the proportion of the hydrosol, but some disadvantages such as popping, slow-drying and abnormal high viscosity tend to be noticeable as weight percent of the hydrosol based on all binders is more than 35%. The weight percent of the hydrosol in the binder should preferably be in the range of 25 to 35% for better balanced properties. AFM images confirm that well-designed hydrosols play an important role in dispersing pigments, which contributes to a smooth and glossy film.

Experimental

All monomers, ammonium persulfate (APS), sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃), nonylphenol polyglycol ether (Tx-10), sodium alkylated diphenyl ether disulfonate (RHODACAL DSB) (all Qingzhou Pada Chemical Co.), various coating aids (Henkel aids; all Shenzhen Ocean Power Industrial Co.), pigments, hexamethoxymethylmelamine(HMMM), isopropanol, ethylene glycol

monobutyl ether, azobisisobutyronitrile and mercapto-ethanol (all Qingdao Chemical Co.) were used as received.

Synthesis of the hydroxyl acrylic latex : The latex was prepared by seeded semi-continuous emulsion polymerization. The synthesis was performed in a four-neck 500 ml flask equipped with a stirrer, a thermometer, a reflux condenser and two dropping funnels. The stirring rate was kept at 150 rpm throughout the synthesis. The reaction temperature was controlled with a thermostated water. The Tg of the latex polymer as calculated using the Fox equation (here referred to as Fox Tg) was designed to be about 10° according to Fox equation, and the contents of AA and HEA were designed respectively to be about 1.0 wt. % and 6.0 wt. % based on all monomers. Based on the above design, the recipe for the latex as listed in Table 5 is arrived at.

Table 5. Recipe for synthesis of the latex

No.	Feed component	Weight (g)
I	Styrene (St)	20.0
	Methyl methacrylate (MMA)	70.0
	Butyl acrylate (BA)	76.0
	Acrylic acid (AA)	2.0
	Hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA)	12.0
II	Deionized water	156.0
	Tx-10	5.6
	DSB (45 wt. %)	4.8
III	Ammonium persulfate	0.8
	Sodium bicarbonate	0.8
	Deionized water	52.0

Portion II and one third of portion I were charged into the flask. The mixture were emulsified by stirring, and heated. When the temperature reached to 80°, one third of portion III was added and the system was held at this temperature for 30 min. The remainder of the portion I and portion III were then added dropwise to the reactor in the temperature range of 80 to 85° over a period of 1.5 h. After the addition of all the ingredients was completed, the reaction temperature of 80 to 85° was maintained for an additional 1.5 h. The products were allowed to cool down to ambient temperature, and neutralized with ammonia to a pH of 7.5~8.0. Finally, the product was obtained by screening the latex with 300 mesh screen. The main characteristics of the latex are shown in Table 6.

Synthesis of acrylic hydrosols : Acrylic hydrosols were prepared by solution polymerization of the same mixture of monomers as given in Table 7 in the mixture of isopropanol and ethylene glycol monobutyl ether (32 : 68

Table 6. Main characteristics of the latex

Properties	Values
Non-volatile (NV, wt. %)	44.1
Viscosity (mPa.s)	290
dz (nm)*	156.4
dn (nm)*	152.0
dv (nm)*	154.9
dv/dn*	1.019

*dz : Z average diameter; dn : number average diameter; dv : volume average diameter; dv/dn : the polydispersity of the particle size.

Table 7. Monomer formulations of hydrosols (wt. %)

Sl. no.	AA	MMA	BA	St	HEA
1.	4.0	36.0	40.0	10.0	10.0
2.	5.0	35.0	40.0	10.0	10.0
3.	6.0	34.0	40.0	10.0	10.0
4.	7.0	33.0	40.0	10.0	10.0
5.	8.0	32.0	40.0	10.0	10.0
6.	10.0	30.0	40.0	10.0	10.0
7.	12.0	28.0	40.0	10.0	10.0
8.	14.0	26.0	40.0	10.0	10.0
9.	6.0	36.0	43.0	10.0	5.0
10.	6.0	38.0	46.0	10.0	0.0

g/g) with azobisisobutyronitrile as an initiator and mercaptoethanol as a chain transfer agent. The polymerizations were carried out in the same equipment as described earlier. The reaction temperature was controlled with a thermostated oil. The typical Fox Tg of the hydrosol resins was designed to be about 10°, and the typical contents of AA and HEA were designed respectively to be 6.0 wt. % and 10.0 wt. % based on all monomers. When the contents of AA or HEA were modulated, those of MMA and BA were also changed correspondingly to keep Fox Tg of recipes at about 10°. The typical recipe for synthesis of the hydrosols is listed in Table 8. Portion II was charged into the flask, and heated. When the temperature reached to 100°, portion I was added dropwise to the reactor at the temperature range of 100 to 105°

Table 8. Recipe for synthesis of the hydrosols

No.	Feed component	Weight (g)
I	Monomers	200.0
	Mercaptoethanol	1.8
	Azobisisobutyronitrile	2.0
II	Ethylene glycol monobutyl ether	68.0
	Isopropanol	32.0
III	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethyl ethanolamine	10.0~35.0
	Deionized water	86.2~61.2
	Total	400.0

over a period of 2.5 h. After the addition of all the ingredients was completed, the reaction temperature of 100 to 105° was maintained for an additional 4.5 h. Then, the system were let to cool down to ambient temperature. Finally, the product was obtained by neutralizing with *N,N*-dimethyl ethanolamine to a pH of 7.5~8.0 and diluting with deionized water to solid contents of about 48%.

Preparation of water-borne coatings : The formulation of water-borne coatings is shown in Table 9. 50 g of R-930 TiO₂, 50 ml of deionized water, 2 g of dispersant (SN-Dispersant 5040) and a little defoamer were charged into a 200 ml sand mill, and ground for 1 h, then filtered through a 300 mesh screen and thickened with SN-Thickener 612 to obtain a white pigment paste. 35 g of P.B.15 Phthalocyanin blue, 10 g of dispersant (Hydropalat^R3275),

Table 9. Formulation of water-borne coatings

No.	Feed component	Weight percents (%)
I	White pigment paste (NV, 49 wt. %)	18.0
	Blue pigment paste (NV, 38 wt. %)	3.0
II	HMMM (NV, 55 wt. %)	6.0
III	Binders (NV, 45 wt. %)*	70.0
IV	Defoamer (Nopco 8034)	About 0.1
	Thickeners (SN-Thickener 636)	About 2.9
	Total	100.0

*Combination of the hydrosols and the latex (15 : 85 g/g based on solids except for the section where the effect of ratio of the hydrosols to latex is examined).

55 ml of deionized water, and a little defoamer were charged into a 200 ml sand mill, ground for 1 h, then filtered through a 300 mesh screen and thickened with SN-Thickener 612 to obtain a blue pigment paste. 9 g of the white pigment paste, 1.5 g of the blue pigment paste, 3 g of HMMM, 35 g of binders and a little defoamer were charged into a 150 ml beaker under stirring. After the addition of the above ingredients, the mixture was stirred for an additional 15 min, and filtered through a 300 mesh screen. Finally, the coating was obtained by thickening the mixture with SN-Thickener 636.

Property analysis : The molecular weights of polymers were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) using Waters 1515 isocratic HPL where Waters 2414 used as refractive index detector, tetrahydrofuran as a flowing phase and polystyrene as a calibration standard sample. Particle size and its distribution of the latex were measured by dynamic light scattering employing a Malven zetasizer 3000HS particle sizer. Glass transition

temperature (T_g) were measured with a NETZSCH 204 differential scanning calorimeter (DSC). Samples were encapsulated in standard aluminum DSC pans and heated from -50 to 200° at the rate of $20^\circ/\text{min}$ under N_2 atmosphere. A Nanosurf Easy Scan atomic force microscopy (AFM) was used to examine the surface structure of the film. Viscosity was measured at $23-25^\circ$ by a NDJ-1 rotary viscometer (Shanghai Scale Instrument). Coating films were prepared by casting water-borne coatings on standardized galvanized iron sheets which were then baked at $150-155^\circ$ for 15 min after surface dried in air. Impact resistance was evaluated with a QCJ film impact testing machine (Tianjin Weida Testing Machine Manufacturer). Gloss was measured at 45° reflectance with a KJZ-1B glossmeter (Tianjin Weida Testing Machine Manufacturer). Adhesion was evaluated with a QFZ adhesion testing machine (Tianjin Weida Testing Machine Manufacturer). Grade 1 represents the best. Water-resistance was evaluated by immersing the test panel in hot water at $50-53^\circ$. The water-resistance is represented by the time when the

first blisters were perceived. Pencil hardness was measured by the method described in the literature⁶.

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